

Some Studies on Mixed Ligand Complexes of Co(II), Ni(II) and Zn(II) with Hydrazine and Oxalic Acid

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Mixed ligand complexes of Co(II), Ni(II) and Zn(II) with hydrazine and oxalate ion as ligands have been prepared by simple methods in aqueous medium and characterized by elemental analysis, thermal and infrared studies and magnetic measurements.

SOME complexes of Co(II), Ni(II) and Zn(II) salts with hydrazine have been reported¹⁻⁴, but relatively little work has been reported on mixed ligand complexes of these metals containing hydrazine and oxalic acid. We have prepared such mixed ligand complexes by reacting hydrazine containing complexes with potassium oxalate in aqueous medium which have been studied by different techniques.

Experimental

The chemicals used were B.D.H. or E. Merck products. The hydrazine hydrate (Riedal) was used in the preparations. The IR spectra of the complexes were recorded as KBr disc on a Perkin-Elmer model No. 700 spectrophotometer. For estimation of metals, known weight of the metal complex was dissolved in dil. sulphuric acid and heated with 5 ml conc. nitric acid. The solution was evaporated to fumes, diluted with distilled water, and nearly neutralized with 1.0 M NaOH. Zinc in the solution was determined volumetrically by EDTA titration using eriochrome Black-T as indicator⁵, cobalt was estimated gravimetrically as cobalt sulphate⁶ and nickel was estimated gravimetrically as nickel dimethyl glyoximate⁵. Oxalate was estimated gravimetrically as calcium oxalate monohydrate⁶. Sulphate was estimated gravimetrically as BaSO₄. Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were estimated by element analysis technique. The hydrazine content was determined by potassium iodate method⁵. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made in a Guoy balance using CoHg(SCN)₄ as the calibrant.

Preparation and characterization of complexes :

The complex, sulphato-bis(hydrazine)cobalt(II)-monohydrate (I) was prepared by mixing cold aqueous solutions of cobalt sulphate and hydrazine hydrate in mole ratio of 1 : 3. The light pink precipitate was washed and dried in a desiccator. (Found : Co, 24.52 ; N, 23.41 ; H₂O, 7.2 ; SO₄, 40.82 ; N₂H₄, 26.5. Calcd. for [Co(N₂H₄)₂·H₂OOSO₄] : Co, 24.9 ; N, 23.62 ; H₂O, 7.6 ; SO₄, 40.5 ; N₂H₄, 27.0%.)

The complex mono oxalato-bis(hydrazine)Co(II) dihydrate (II) was prepared by reacting the complex (I) with hot potassium oxalate solution. The bright deep red complex was filtered, washed with cold water and ether and dried in a desiccator. (Found : Co, 23.9 ; C, 9.73 ; N, 22.53 ; H₂O, 14.21 ; N₂H₄, 22.25 ; C₂O₄, 36.0. Calcd. for [Co(N₂H₄)₂·C₂O₄]·2H₂O ; Co, 23.86 ; C, 9.72 ; N, 22.67 ; H₂O, 14.57 ; N₂H₄, 25.91 ; C₂O₄, 35.63%.)

The complex, tris(hydrazine)Ni(II)sulphate monohydrate (III) was prepared by shaking concentrated solution of nickel sulphate in aqueous medium and hydrazine hydrate. The thick polymeric violet coloured precipitate was washed with water and collected in a desiccator. (Found : Ni, 21.37 ; N, 31.18 ; H₂O, 6.7 ; SO₄, 35.7 ; N₂H₄, 34.31. Calcd. for [Ni(N₂H₄)₃]SO₄·H₂O ; Ni, 21.84 ; N, 31.26 ; H₂O, 6.7 ; SO₄, 35.72 ; N₂H₄, 35.72%.)

MonooxalatomonohydrazineNi(II) monohydrate (IV) was prepared by shaking complex (III) with cold aqueous solution of potassium oxalate for several hr and then digesting with shaking on a water bath. The violet complex changed to greenish blue. The complex was washed with cold water and dried in a desiccator. (Found : Ni, 29.1 ; C, 12.51 ; N, 14.12 ; N₂H₄, 14.51, C₂O₄, 44.3 ; H₂O, 9.52. Calcd. for [NiN₂H₄C₂O₄]·H₂O ; Ni, 29.84 ; C, 12.2 ; N, 14.23 ; N₂H₄, 16.26 ; C₂O₄, 44.73 ; H₂O, 9.15%.)

Hydrazine-aquoZn(II)sulphate complex (V) was prepared by shaking concentrated solution of zinc sulphate with aqueous hydrazine hydrate. Bright white complex precipitated which is polymeric and adheres to the filter paper. (Found : Zn, 28.70 ; N, 18.41 ; SO₄, 41.80 ; H₂O, 8.0 ; N₂H₄, 20.0. Calcd. for [Zn(N₂H₄)_{1.8}·H₂O]SO₄ ; Zn, 28.75 ; N, 18.46 ; SO₄, 42.21 ; H₂O, 7.91 ; N₂H₄, 21.10%.)

MonooxalatomonohydrazineZn(II) tetrahydrate (VI) was prepared by shaking freshly prepared complex (V) and concentrated solution of potassium oxalate. (Found : Zn, 25.34 ; N, 10.80 ; C₂O₄, 34.42 ; H₂O, 25.20 ; N₂H₄, 11.83. Calcd. for [Zn·C₂O₄·N₂H₄] 4H₂O ; Zn, 25.47 ; N, 10.87 ; C₂O₄, 34.18 ; H₂O, 27.90 ; N₂H₄ ; 12.43%.)

Results and Discussion

Thermal effect : The complexes (I) and (II) were heated separately. At 110° complex (I) was stable and did not show any loss in weight. However, if heated at 160° for 1 hr, the loss in weight was 7.2%, while the hydrazine content remained unaltered. The colour of the complex changed to violet. Complex (II) was less stable to heat. It lost 14.21% of its weight at 120°, excluding a small amount of hydrazine lost at that temperature. The loss of hydrazine content in complex (II) was found even at room temperature.

Complex (III) was found to be quite stable towards heat and storage. Brightness of the colour remained the same even at 160°. The total loss in weight was found to be 6.7%. Complex (IV) was found to be less stable than complex (III) and it was found to lose 10% of its weight at 110°. A small percentage of hydrazine was also lost, while the colour of the complex changed to sky blue.

Complex (V) did not lose weight at 110°, but complex (VI) lost its weight to a large extent (~14%). The complexes were further heated at 175-180° when the complex (V) lost 8%, while complex (VI) lost 25.2% of their weight. However, no hydrazine was lost in either of the two complexes.

shoulder at 1170 cm^{-1} in complex (I) is indicative of the monodentate sulphato group.

In complexes (II), (IV) and (VI), the carboxylate region (1800-1600 cm^{-1}) is very important. A very strong band at about 1635 cm^{-1} in all these complexes is due to coordinated oxalate in the complexes. The broadening of these carboxylate bands is due to the presence of coordinated hydrazine in the complexes. The NH_2 bonding modes of hydrazine⁸ are expected in the same region as that of the carboxylate group.

Very strong resolved bands at about 795 cm^{-1} in complexes (II), (IV) and (VI) may be attributed⁹ to M—O stretching and suggest bonding between the metal and the oxalato oxygen atom¹⁰.

A strong and broad band at 3500-3150 cm^{-1} in complex (I) consists of three very sharp bands at 3425, 3325 and 3200 cm^{-1} . The band at 3425 cm^{-1} is due to the coordinated water, as it is lost on heating the complex (I) at 160°. The other two bands at 3325 and 3200 cm^{-1} become stronger and sharper which may be attributed to NH_2 stretching modes of coordinated hydrazine⁸.

Magnetic studies : For complexes (I), (II), (III) and (IV), the effective magnetic moment was found

TABLE 1—PROMINENT INFRARED ABSORPTION FREQUENCIES OF THE COMPLEXES IN cm^{-1}

Assignment	Complex (I)	Complex (II)	Complex (III)	Complex (IV)	Complex (V)	Complex (VI)
	Frequencies in cm^{-1}					
H_2O Stretching modes	3425 (s)	3460 (b)	3450 (b)	3450 (b)	3550 (sh)	3550 (sh)
NH_2 Stretching	3325 (s) 3270 (sh) 3200 (m)	3290 (s)	3250 (s)	3290 (s) 3250 (s) 3165 (m)	3450 (sh) 3270 (s) 3160 (sh)	3510 (b) 3450 (s) 3160 (sh)
NH_2 Bending	1605 (s) 1580 (m)	1590 (m)	1610 (s)	—	1580 (sh)	1610 (s)
N—N Stretching	978 (m)	978 (m)	980 (m)	985 (m)	960 (sh)	985 (m)
C—O Stretching (Carboxyl group)	—	1635 (s)	—	1643 (s)	—	1640 (s)
M—O Stretching (Metal-oxygen stretching)	—	795 (s)	—	804 (s)	—	810 (s)
SO_4 Stretching	1170 (sh) 1120 (s) 1080 (sh)	—	1100 (s)	—	1100 (b)	—

Infrared studies : The prominent infrared frequencies for the complexes have been included in Table 1. It has been suggested⁶ that N-N stretching frequency is diagnostic⁷ of coordinated hydrazine acting as monodentate⁴ or bridging ligand. In complexes (I) to (VI), medium-sharp bands have been found in the region 985-948 cm^{-1} , which strongly suggest that hydrazine is bridging in all the complexes. In case of complex (V), the band appears only as a shoulder at 960 cm^{-1} which is due to an overlap of band for the anionic sulphate.

Sulphato group is monodentate in complex (I) but uncoordinated in complexes (III) and (V). A very strong and sharp band at 1120 cm^{-1} along with one very strong shoulder at 1080 cm^{-1} and a weak

to be 4.81, 4.826, 2.9 and 3.5 B.M., respectively. The magnetic moments for complexes (I) and (II) suggest an octahedral arrangement¹¹. The magnetic values for complexes (III) and (IV) indicate that Ni(II) is in octahedral arrangement in complex (III) while it is in tetrahedral arrangement in complex (IV).

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MISHRA, MISHRA & CHOUBEY : SOME STUDIES ON MIXED LIGAND COMPLEXES OF Co(II), Ni(II), ETC.

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